

The Impact of Environmental Factors on E-Government Implementation: The Case of Jordan

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Abstract: *With the latest revolution of science and technology, and in particular information and communication technologies (ICTs), the need for computerization has been identified in most countries and Jordan is no exception. One of the major dimensions for this revolution is the development of the E-Government. The purpose of this paper is to explore the realities of the e-government as well as to examine the environmental factors for its implementation in Jordan. A quantitative research methodology using a survey questionnaire was selected as the primary data collection method for this study. The factors need to be assessed are Regulatory and Legal issues, Support Industries for E-Government, Legacy Systems and Old Mindsets, Competition Environment, External Support, and Intergovernmental Relationship. This research uses exploratory factor analysis to identify the main factors that may influence E-government adoption in Jordan.*

According to the research findings, only two factors were found to be important in affecting e-government implementation in Jordan and they are support industries, Legacy and old mindsets.

Key Words: *E-Government, Environmental Factors, ICT, Jordan.*

1. Introduction

Since the end of the last century, computers have become a widespread phenomenon in most developed and developing countries (Aladwani, 2003; Mofleh; Wanous and Strachan, 2008). In the last decade, the Arab world in general, and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan specifically, have witnessed a rapid and comprehensive revolution in information technology (Al-Jaghoub and Westrup, 2003). In Jordan, the existence of personal computers in homes has become increasingly essential to modern life (Ahmad and Zink, 1998; Al Nagi and Hamdan, 2009).

E-government is a relatively new area of study in the Information Systems (IS) field that is concerned with use of ICT by the government agencies to electronically deliver its services (Al-Omari and Al-Omari, 2006). According to Carter and Belanger (2005), the relationship of government with recipients of its electronic services is characterized as; government to citizen (G2C), government to business (G2B); government to employees (G2E) and government to government (G2G). Generally, e-government is considered as a new and emerging area of interest in the field e-business that employs ICTs to enhance the access to and delivery of government information and services to citizens, businesses, government employees, and other agencies (AbuShanab and Pearson, 2007; Elsheikh et al., 2008).

The United Nations e-Government Survey of the year 2010 indicates that citizens are benefiting from

more advanced e-service delivery, better access to information, more efficient government management and improved interactions with governments (Siau and Long, 2006). This is primarily a result of the increasing use of information and communications technology by the public sector. Most countries have published tremendous amount of information online, many going beyond basic websites to provide national portals that serve as major starting points for users to connect to government services in different ministries. At the same time, many developing countries need to devote additional efforts to transactional services as well as the electronic means of engaging citizens in public consultation and decision-making.

In Jordan, as one of the developing countries, the e-Government program was a national initiative (Samaha and Samad, 2007; Elsheikh; Cullen and Hobbs, 2008). The program seeks to achieve greater efficiency in government performance by raising the level of service delivery to citizens and investors from all segments of the society. According to the official site of the Jordanian E-Government, the vision of the program is "An essential and active participant in the economic and social development through the use of information and communication technology to enable easy access to government information and services for all Users regardless of their geographic location or economic status or professional capacity". Despite the benefits and opportunities delivered by e-

government, the program still faces many challenges (Shannak, 2013). This research is trying to examine the environmental challenges that inhabit the use and adoption of e-government within Jordanian government.

2. Literature Review

There are many studies that discussed the factors that affect the implementation of E-government. According to J.Ramon Garcia and Theresa Paedo (2005), restrictive laws and regulations developed prior to or in ignorance of technologies relevant to e-government can affect its success. One strategy for responding to these challenges is to invest in changes to the regulatory environment that allow for or enable adoption of emerging technologies. Digital signature technologies, for example, required changes in most jurisdictions before they could be adopted for use. Developing appropriate government-wide IT policies and standards can also provide an adequate framework for e-government initiatives to be successful. In this regard, governments are developing IT policies and standards and making them available through their official Web sites (Gibbs; Kraemer and Dedrick, 2003).

Ahmad and Hussein Al Omari (2006), stated that the legal part of e-government is very important, where the new procedures and other government activities have to be formally regulated. The organizational change, leadership and governance reform and the new channels of services, has to be legally issued. This includes laws, bylaws, directives and all other regularity issues that concern government service delivery. The legal umbrella is the safety valve for all government activities. Each organization that wishes to implement e-initiative has to do a separate legal assessment for its case.

To overcome most of the regulatory and legal issues, the government of Jordan has issued the Electronic Transaction Temporary Law No. 85 of 2001 (ETL) in the year 2001. The main objective of the law is to regulate electronic transactions conducted by electronic facilities. The ETL law has many articles explaining the conditions and policies for most of the adaptation of the electronic means. In general, nothing in the current legal framework explicitly prevents electronic online transactions with the Government Ministries. On the contrary, current legislation would seem to support the adoption of

electronic transactions where there is no doubt about the authenticity of the applicant.

According to Hart and Saunders 1998; Hu et al. (2006), regulatory environment identified as coercive pressure on assimilation E-Government that can arise from government as regulator or policy from professional as well as legislative influences. Past researches have shown coercive pressure to be a significant factor in adoption of innovation. Prior studies have showed that regulatory support is a critical environmental factor that tends to affect e-government usage.

In regards to the Support Industries for E-Government, there are roles for the private sector uniquely positioned to help governments to build and manage the e-government in a perfect way; the industrial sectors have taken projects regarding to develop the e-government in providing fully understand the state's needs and then offer the state a set of proven and varied skills, including Web site management, graphic design, usability design and implementation, multilingual services, payment processing, security, application development, customer support, and marketing.

There are many studies that talk about the competency environment and its affect in e-government implementation. According to Lacoivu et al., (1995) and Zhu et al., (2003) competition environment drives e-government implementation and assimilation, and drive to initiate and adopt innovations to maintain their competitive edge.

G. Premkumar; Margaret Roberts, (1998) defines the external support as the availability of support for implementing and using an information system. It ensures that the availability of external support to be positively related to e-government adoption.

A major point of concern in Jordan is Legacy System and Old Mindsets. According to Claudio Ciborra, (2005), the point in the e-government is that the government institution required to pay for services, presently the value of these services is extremely difficult to estimate, let alone understand the willingness and ability of the Jordanian population to pay for them. And to understand that these technologies is not cheap and it is complicated because it will serve the institution and citizen in a modern way.

3. Research Model and Hypothesis

From the previous literature review and from the studies conducted by the authors above we conclude that the factors mentioned will be standing in the case of Jordan. According to the purpose of this study that is to find some of the environmental factors that affect e-government implementation. The factors need to be assessed are Regulatory and

Legal issues, Support Industries for E-Government, Legacy Systems and Old Mindsets, Competition Environment, External Support, and Intergovernmental Relationship. Research hypotheses are generated to examine their affect on the adoption of e-government as shown in table 1 below.

Table 1
Summary of the factors and hypotheses of the research study

Factors	Hypotheses
Regulatory and Legal Issues	H1. The regulatory environment is positively related to E-Government implementation.
Support industries for e-government	H2. The innovation and development in the industrial sector will positively affect the E-Government implementation.
Legacy systems and old mindsets	H3. The legal systems and old mindsets positively affect the E-Government implementation.
Competition environment	H4. The competition environment is positively related to E-Government implementation.
External support	H5. The greater the external support for communication technology the more likely the E-Government implementation will be adopted.
Intergovernmental relationship	H6. The intergovernmental relationships are positively related to E-Government.

According to the previous literature, we concluded that there are six factors associated with the environmental factors that influence e-government implementation. These six factors are considered the independent variables that will be used to assess and examine their affect on e-government performance that considered the dependent variable as shown in figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Research Framework

4. Methodology

Research methods can be classified in various ways; however one of the most common distinctions is between qualitative and quantitative research methods (Babbie, 2004; Bryman and Bell, 2007). Quantitative research methods were originally developed in the natural sciences to study natural phenomena. Examples of quantitative methods include survey methods, laboratory experiments, formal methods and numerical methods such as mathematical modeling. Examples of qualitative methods are action research and case study research (Michael D. Myers, 1997).

A quantitative research methodology using a survey questionnaire was selected as the primary data collection method for this study. A survey questionnaire was utilized as it is inexpensive, less time consuming and has the ability to provide data from the research sample. This study aims to clarify the relationship between the environmental factors and e-government implementation in Jordan. However, in order to conduct the questionnaire survey, the research population and sample must be determined as explained in the following sections.

4.1 Research Population and Sample

A population is a group of individual's persons, objects, or items from which sample are taken for measurement (Webster, 1985). The population of this study is the employees of the Jordanian Ministry of Communication (JMC). The unit of analysis will be the staffs who carry managerial positions within the JMC. The sample is a finite part of a statistical population whose properties are studied to gain information about the whole.

The sampling process contains major steps; the first step is defining the population. The population of this study again is the managerial staff at the JMC. The second step is determining the sampling design; the researcher decided to use the probability sampling and specially the simple random sampling in order to have some known, non-zero chance or probability of being selected as sample subjects (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970; Uma sekaran & Roger bougie; 2010). The next step in the sampling process is determining the sample size; according to many references, the researcher concluded that there are many factors play a role in determining the sample size such as the research objective, the desired precision, and the cost and time constraints. In this case, the sample size is 160 because we have

6 factors (Cochran, 1977; Ellen Taylor-Powell, 1998; Sekaran and Bougie, 2010).

4.2 Research Instrument

The questionnaire in our study consists of three parts; the first part aims to get general information about the organization that the respondents work for. The second part contains questions aim to find out the relationship between the environmental factors and the E-government implementation. The last part aims to measure directly the dependence variable itself. Due to time and cost limitations, we only received 141 questionnaires out of 200 distributed in the Ministry of Communication and Information Technology.

5. Testing the Research Hypotheses

The research hypotheses that have been formulated from the literature will be tested in this chapter. The results will determine the most important factors that affect and influence the implementation of e-government. In addition, the results of the analysis will be used to refine the original research model. The most appropriate tool that been used to test the research hypotheses is the multiple linear regression analysis. Multiple linear regression attempts to examine the relationship between two or more explanatory variables and a response variable by fitting a linear equation to observed data (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010). Therefore, a stepwise multiple linear regressions will be used in this research.

To find out the factors that affect the implementation of e-government implementation, a multiple linear regression will be applied to test the research hypotheses. The dependent variable is e-government implementation is calculated by the sum of the scores of the seven variables that include (profit, customer satisfaction, quantity of services, time saving, and the probability of having mistakes ... etc). The six independent variables mentioned above will be examined against the dependent variable.

The result of the stepwise regression for the six independent variables that make up the original model identified two variables that have significant affect predicting the e-government implementation with p-values <0.05 as summarized in table 2 below.

These variables are support industries for E-government and Legacy and old mindsets.

Table 2

Results of the stepwise regression that shows the significant variables of the research model

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.372	.633		6.902	.000
	R	.181	.093	.273	1.939	.058
	SUPPORT	-.213	.091	-.375	-2.345	.023
	LEGACY	-.281	.125	-.284	-2.242	.029
	COMPETITION	-.136	.083	-.264	-1.636	.108
	EXTERNAL	-.048	.104	-.062	-.465	.644
	INTERGOV	.017	.083	.029	.208	.836

a. Dependent Variable: PERFORMANCE

The non-significant variables that were excluded from the original model with P-values > 0.05 are four as shown in table 3 below. These variables are regulatory and legal issues, competition environment, external support, and intergovernmental relationships.

Table 3

Results of stepwise regression that shows the excluded variable from the research model

Model		Beta In	T	Sig
4	regulatory and legal issues	0.273	1.939	0.058
	competition environment	-0.264	-1.636	0.108
	external support	-0.62	-0.465	0.644
	Intergovernmental relationships.	0.029	0.208	0.836

The model summary in table 4 below includes the value of R² that shows how much the variance in the dependent variable e-government implementation is explained by the two independent variables. The R² value is 0.308, which means that the research model (which includes the independent variables) explain only 30.8% of the variance in e-government implementation.

Table 4

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.555 ^a	.308	.231	.35235

a. Predictors: (Constant), INTERGOV, LEGACY, R, EXTERNAL, SUPPORT, COMPETITION

Evaluating the importance of each independent variable on predicting the e-government implementation within the ministry of communications and information technologies can be examined by the coefficient table (standardized coefficients) obtained from the analysis. The coefficient table, table 2 above shows that the largest beta coefficient is -0.375 which is for support industries for e-government. This means that this variable makes the strongest

contribution to predict and explain the e-government implementation in Jordan. The second beta coefficient is -0.284 which is for legacy systems and old mindsets. Final results are shown in table 5 below.

Table 5

Results of the regression analysis of the research hypotheses of the original model

Independent Variables	Hypotheses	Result
Regulatory and legal issues	The regulatory environment is positively related to E-Government implementation.	Not Supported
Support industries	The innovation and development in the industrial sector will positively affect the E-Government implementation.	Supported
Legacy systems and old mindsets	The legacy systems and old mindsets negatively affect the E-Government implementation.	Supported
Competition environment	The competition environment is positively related to E-Government implementation.	Not Supported
External support	The greater the external support for communication technology the more likely the E-Government implementation will be adopted.	Not Supported
Intergovernmental relationship	The intergovernmental relationships are positively related to E-Government.	Not Supported

6. Research Findings and Recommendations

This study examines the different environmental factors related to e-government implementation in Jordan. The research results indicate that, Support industries for e-government and Legacy systems and old mindset are the main factors that affect e-government implementation in Jordan. According to Angela Skinner (Angela Skinner, NIC Company), the private sector is uniquely positioned to help governments build and manage a successful e-Government initiative but not all providers are alike. Major point of concern in Jordan is Legacy System and Old Mindsets that since citizens will be required to pay for services, presently the value of these services is extremely difficult to estimate, let alone understand the willingness and ability of the Jordanian population to pay for them.

According to the analysis, the researchers found that the Regulatory and Legal Issues, competition environment, External support and the intergovernmental factors didn't have major impact on the e-government implementation while the support industries and legacy systems and old mindsets are the main factors that affect the implementation of e-government in Jordan.

The researchers recommend redistribution of the questionnaire for more than one governmental agency giving enough time for the employees with

Arabic translation to understand the questionnaire better and getting approvals in advance. The researchers also recommend conducting meetings with the concerned employees to illustrate the importance of the research goals.

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